

MANAGEMENT OF STAFF IN HYBRID AND REMOTE WORK MODELS

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The changes that occurred in the global business landscape during the pandemic highlighted the importance of flexibility in work models, leading to the widespread adoption of hybrid and remote working formats. These transformations made it essential for employers and managers to develop new management strategies. Effective management of staff in hybrid and remote work models involves not only technological infrastructure and process optimization, but also complex issues such as employee motivation, emotional engagement, performance evaluation, and the preservation of organizational culture. This article provides an in-depth analysis of the advantages, challenges, and implications of this management model, supported by statistical findings from reputable international research organizations such as Gallup and McKinsey. Furthermore, current practices and experiences in Azerbaijan are reviewed, and the transition strategies of various companies to hybrid and remote work are analyzed.

Keywords: staff management, hybrid work, remote work, organizational culture, strategic management, motivation, performance evaluation.

Introduction. In the modern era, technological advancements, international economic changes, and socio-cultural transformations have led to the emergence of new management models in the business world. Among these models, hybrid and remote work formats have gained particular attention. As the demand for flexibility and adaptability in labor relations increases, organizations strive to align their work processes with this new environment. Hybrid and remote work models not only provide employees with more flexible and balanced working conditions but also present a range of advantages and challenges for organizations. The necessity for new management approaches has become evident, making issues such as employee motivation, performance, communication, and overall management more relevant than ever.

Analysis of recent research and publications. Numerous international studies indicate that remote and hybrid work models present both opportunities and challenges. This article references research from reputable organizations such as McKinsey, Deloitte, and Gallup, as well as scientific works by both local and international researchers including B. Wang, Y. Liu, N. Bloom, Ş. Rzayev, E. Yusifov, R. Aliyev, among others. A comprehensive analysis of these studies reveals that while hybrid and remote work models contribute to short-term productivity and satisfaction increases, their sustainable and effective implementation requires corresponding strategic changes in management approaches. In the modern era, staff management increasingly relies on flexibility, empathy, and technological skills.

Objective of the study. The aim of this study is to investigate the impact of widely adopted hybrid and remote work models on staff management in the modern labor market, to identify the strengths and weaknesses of these models, and to analyze effective management strategies in order to provide relevant recommendations.

Main material of the research. Over the past 20 years, rapid advancements in international technology, along with the expansion and improvement of technological capabilities, have had a significant impact on all sectors, including management in the business world. Wars, pandemics, and especially the COVID-19 pandemic created a global state of emergency that necessitated the performance of many processes and operations remotely, leading to the widespread adoption of hybrid and remote work models [5]. Remote work refers to employees performing their job functions from home or any other distant location with the help of technological tools.

Hybrid work, on the other hand, involves a combination of both remote and office-based work [6]. In the hybrid work model, employees work some days in the office and some days outside the office. The first experiences with remote work began to emerge in the late 20th century in the USA and European countries. Subsequently, the rapid and widespread adoption of the internet, its accessibility, the implementation of cloud technology, as well as the emergence and significant advancement of mobile devices, have enhanced the functionality of hybrid and remote work models [9]. However, during the COVID-19 pandemic, remote work became a necessity for companies, including those in the construction industry [13; 19; 20]. This model played a crucial role in enabling agile decision-making and reducing companies' financial expenditures. Therefore, even after the pandemic, many companies continued to implement this model according to their operational directions [5]. Initially, numerous global companies primarily operating in technology and finance sectors took significant steps to adopt the hybrid and remote work models. Companies such as Google, Amazon, Microsoft, Samsung, and others adapted their employees' work modes to align with hybrid and remote work models [12].

In the United States, European countries, and many other technologically advanced nations, the transition to hybrid and remote work models has been supported both legislatively and at the organizational strategy level within companies [17]. Although the hybrid and remote work models are not yet widespread in Azerbaijan, during the COVID-19 pandemic, they were extensively applied in the ICT, banking, and education sectors [1; 2; 10]. However, legal and organizational

frameworks necessary for the broad implementation of hybrid and remote work models in Azerbaijan have not yet been fully developed.

The transition to hybrid and remote work models is developing at varying levels across the world. The extent of companies' adoption of this model in the business sector across different regions of the world is illustrated in Figure 1 [11].

Figure 1. Distribution of Companies Adopting Hybrid/Remote Work Models by Region, (%)

Source: [11]

The implementation of hybrid and remote work models has led to the emergence of new approaches to staff management in companies. Specifically, evaluating the performance of employees working remotely from different locations and maintaining the organizational culture of the company are considered major challenges in managing staff under this model [18]. Many different issues and problems arise in managing staff within hybrid and remote work models, including:

a) Communication Challenges – When employees work traditionally in the office, information exchange happens more easily and promptly. However, in hybrid and remote work models, difficulties arise in the flow of information, increasing the risk of misunderstandings and delays [14].

b) Motivation Problems – Employees working outside the office are not only physically separated but also disconnected from the company's organizational culture. Due to limited contact with the organizational culture, employees' emotional attachment to the work environment decreases [8]. According to Gallup's 2023 "State of the Global Workplace" report, only 33% of remote workers feel emotionally connected to their work. This indicates weakened contact with organizational culture among remote employees, making motivation and engagement priority issues for managers [8].

c) Performance Evaluation – In the traditional model, managers observe employees in person, interact with them, and assess their performance. In hybrid and remote models, where direct observation is not possible, both managers and employees must adapt to the new rules of this model during the transition [6].

d) Security – In hybrid and remote work models, employees use personal computers and open internet networks, which pose risks to corporate data security. This can particularly create problems in safeguarding information related to legal, financial, and other sensitive areas [14].

e) Weakening of Team Spirit Culture – In an office environment, employees engage in informal communication, shared lunches, and participate together in various events, all of which strengthen team spirit. In hybrid and remote work models, the significant reduction in communication and lack of social interaction lead to a weakening of team spirit [5].

Opportunities Created by Hybrid and Remote Work Models in Management:

a) Employee Satisfaction – Hybrid and remote work models allow employees to balance work and personal life. This model increases employee satisfaction, which in turn strengthens their commitment to the company. It is especially attractive to employees with families. The levels of employee satisfaction across different work models are shown in Figure 2 [7].

Figure 2. Employee Satisfaction Across Different Work Models, (%)

Source: [7]

b) **Cost Reduction** – One of the main advantages of the hybrid and remote work models for companies is the reduction of office expenses, utilities, and logistics costs. This enables companies to redirect their financial resources toward significant strategic projects [6].

c) **Elimination of Geographic Barriers** – In the traditional work model, companies’ talent pools were limited by physical location. However, in hybrid and remote work models, this limitation is removed. Companies can attract talent not only regionally but also internationally, expanding their talent base beyond geographic constraints [17].

d) **Agile and Transparent Management** – Companies that transition to hybrid and remote work models adapt more flexibly to technological changes. Additionally, they are better equipped to quickly adjust their operations during global crises such as wars or pandemics [7]. According to a 2022 survey by McKinsey, one of the world’s most reputable consulting firms, 58% of respondents reported being more productive under the hybrid work model. This finding confirms that employee control over work schedules and flexible working conditions increase productivity [11] (Figure 3).

Figure 3. McKinsey 2022 Survey Results, (%)

Source: [11]

e) **Environmental Benefits** – Unlike the traditional model, employees in hybrid and remote work models do not need to use transportation for commuting, and internal company transportation usage also decreases. This leads to a reduction in carbon emissions and helps prevent negative impacts on the environment [17].

A 2021 study published by Deloitte, another reputable global company, notes that organizations adopting hybrid work models reduce employee turnover and significantly increase employee satisfaction. This model is presented as an advantage affecting long-term

stability and motivation. Deloitte's "Return to Workplace" survey revealed that approximately 67% of companies kept their employees fully remote in the post-pandemic period; however, 64% of these companies plan to reintegrate employees into hybrid or fully on-site work soon. This trend has become a new norm not only after the pandemic but also within the evolving work culture. Additionally, Deloitte's "Future of Work" survey shows that organizations view the shift to hybrid models not only as agility but also as an opportunity for effective collaboration and performance. Executives prefer to establish a balanced work and office system [7]. According to research results, before

the pandemic, 47% of organizations relied on a single work model, but in the post-pandemic period, this figure changed, and multiple work modes-hybrid or remote-became the norm. In a 2023 survey, 56% of respondents reported working from home at least some days, and 54% were included in the employer's hybrid work option [7]. Companies use various management strategies in hybrid and remote work models. The description of these management strategies, their purpose in application, and the outcomes they enable are shown in Figure 4 [8; 18].

Management Strategy	Description	Objective	Outcome
Establishing Communication Platforms	Organizing Effective Communication through Tools like Teams, Zoom, and Slack	Ensuring Information Flow and Creating a Collaborative Environment	Strengthening Team Spirit and Achieving Agility in the Decision-Making Process
Establishing an Outcome-Based Performance System	Measuring Employee Performance Using Systems like KPI and OKR	Ensuring Effective Distribution of Workload	Achieving a Fair Reward System
Establishing a Virtual Motivation System	Virtual Appreciation Systems, Bonuses, and Non-Monetary Rewards	Maintaining Motivation of Employees Working in Hybrid and Remote Work Models	Increasing Employee Satisfaction
Online Training and Development	Online Courses, Trainings, and Webinars	Support for Professional Development	Enhancing Employees Professionalism and Promoting Innovative Innovations
Psychological Support	Virtual Consultations and Stress Management	Protecting Employees Psychological Well-Being	Stress Management and Ensuring Increased Employee Engagement
Trust-Based Leadership	Supportive Leadership	Encouragement of Autonomy	Development of Responsible Employee Behavior

Figure 4. Effective Management Strategies in Staff Management within Hybrid and Remote Work Models
Source: [8; 18]

Reviewing the management strategies noted in Figure 1, it becomes clear that a successful strategy is not limited to technology alone; these strategies are human-centered and results-oriented [18].

Technological infrastructure plays a crucial role in managing staff within hybrid and remote work models. There are many technological tools to establish effective communication systems among employees and ensure the flow of information. Platforms such as Slack, Microsoft Teams, and Zoom facilitate effective communication, while Miro, Trello, and Notion are widely used for collaboration and project planning. Tools like Office 365 and Google Workspace enable real-time document collaboration and joint work. For monitoring performance and workflow, solutions like Zoho People and BambooHR are important, and in the field of training and development, platforms such as Coursera for Business, Udemy Business, and LinkedIn Learning play a significant role [5; 6].

However, many risks arise in managing staff in hybrid and remote work models. To mitigate these risks, companies seek certain solutions [12]. One major risk is weakened communication and cooling of relationships among team members, which seriously harms team spirit, increases misunderstandings, and causes

emotional distancing among employees. To reduce this risk, frequent virtual meetings and encouragement of informal communication within group chats can be implemented [8]. Another risk involves how employee performance is measured. In the traditional model, performance was primarily assessed through direct observation; however, this approach is ineffective in hybrid and remote work settings. Therefore, implementing results-oriented performance methods in this model can be considered a solution for establishing a fair performance evaluation system [12]. The security of a company's corporate data poses risks in hybrid and remote work models. Problems may arise due to employees' insufficient IT knowledge, the use of personal computers, and other factors that compromise the protection of corporate information. To minimize this risk, employees should participate in IT training, and company accounts must be secured with two-factor authentication [8].

Another risk is the weakening of the company's organizational culture, which reduces employee loyalty and leads to increased turnover. A solution to this issue is the frequent implementation of virtual onboarding programs [5].

Although the hybrid and remote work models are not yet widespread in Azerbaijan, the necessity to adapt to global changes, as well as the parallel implementation of these models alongside traditional ones after the pandemic, have made their adoption essential. Enterprises that previously operated solely within an office environment have begun experimenting with more flexible, technology-driven models that prioritize employee well-being. At the core of this change are hybrid and remote work models [16].

The pandemic period made this transition inevitable and urgent for many organizations. Large and forward-thinking entities, particularly in the banking sector, IT companies, and media organizations, were able to implement these models more smoothly [4]. For example, Kapital Bank adopted a tailored approach by allowing some employees to work fully remotely while others followed a hybrid model, depending on individual needs and the nature of their duties. This approach was particularly successful in fields such as analytics, marketing, and project management. Organizations such as Azercell, ABB, PASHA Bank, and ATL Tech went further by regularly developing “remote work policies” and supporting the transition with internal training programs [15]. These companies went beyond merely providing technical infrastructure; they also implemented programs aimed at equipping managers with the specific skills necessary for remote team management.

One of the key challenges in managing remote and hybrid work was maintaining employee motivation and team spirit. Modern human resources strategies became critical here—many companies gradually implemented quarterly virtual wellbeing events, recognition platforms, digital performance evaluation systems, and psychological support services [4].

Some companies expanded their talent pools by recruiting skilled professionals living in regional areas for remote work. This practice promoted inclusivity and diversification in the labor market. Allowing employees to work not only in the capital but also in other cities enriched organizations' talent strategies over the long term and expanded the boundaries of their talent pools [5].

Conclusion. Due to the rapid development of technology and the necessity created by the global pandemic, hybrid and remote work models have begun to be widely adopted by companies. Unlike traditional work models, these models allow employees to operate without location constraints, thereby increasing both employee satisfaction and operational efficiency. This transformation has simultaneously necessitated the formation of new strategies in workforce management. Issues such as employee motivation, performance measurement, effective communication, and the preservation of corporate culture have become priority areas for management. Modern management approaches now consider results-based performance evaluations, agile leadership, and the integration of technology into management as essential. These changes are also evident in Azerbaijan. Particularly, companies operating in information technology, banking, telecommunications, and internationally connected sectors (such as PASHA

Holding, Azercell, Kapital Bank, ATL Tech, Az-InTelecom) have started implementing hybrid or fully remote work models. Digital platforms are used in these companies to monitor employee performance, while intra-team communication is supported through tools like Slack, Microsoft Teams, and Zoom. However, certain challenges remain for the full and effective implementation of this model in Azerbaijan. In particular, inadequate technological infrastructure in small and medium-sized enterprises, limited remote management skills among managers, and a weak development of trust-based management culture may restrict progress in this area. Globally, hybrid and remote work models offer organizations agile structures and access to a broader talent pool. Successful implementation of these models depends not only on technological resources but also on leadership skills, psychological adaptation, a spirit of collaboration, and strategic approaches. Azerbaijan is also showing progress in this field, and the effective management of these models plays a vital role in modernizing the country's labor market.

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